

Predicting Thinking Time in Chess

An Empirical Study Based on Magnus Carlsen's Blitz Games

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence systems have reached superhuman performance in chess, yet they largely fail to reproduce essential aspects of human behavior, notably the temporal dynamics of decision-making. While recent research has focused on modeling human move selection and playing style, the time humans spend thinking before playing a move remains largely unexplored. This temporal dimension is central to human cognition and plays a key role in both strategic decision-making and the subjective experience of playing chess.

In this work, we investigate whether human thinking time can be empirically modeled from real game data. Focusing on blitz games played by Magnus Carlsen, we construct a dataset from publicly available PGN files in which each move is enriched with temporal, positional, and game-dynamic features. Using this dataset, we evaluate several machine learning approaches, ranging from linear models to non-linear methods such as Random Forests and neural networks, to predict the time spent on individual moves.

Our results show that non-linear models substantially outperform linear baselines, with a Random Forest model explaining up to 50% of the variance in human thinking time. These findings suggest that thinking time is not purely stochastic, but depends on observable features of the position and game context that are accessible in real time. Although limited in scope, this study demonstrates the feasibility of predicting human reflection time and highlights the importance of temporal modeling for human-aligned chess AI.

More broadly, this work opens the door to integrating realistic time management into human-like chess engines and imitation-based systems such as Maia. By enriching move prediction with a temporal component, future AI systems could achieve more coherent human-AI alignment, improved pedagogical value, and a more immersive playing experience. Our implementation and experimental pipeline are enabled here: <https://github.com/elijahlieb/magnus-time-prediction-ml/tree/main>

Introduction

Since the early 2000s, artificial intelligence systems dedicated to chess have undergone spectacular progress. Engines such as Stockfish, Leela Chess Zero, and AlphaZero now dominate competitions between machines and have profoundly transformed strategic understanding of the game. However, these systems are not designed to reproduce human behavior. They compute and execute the best possible moves almost instantaneously, without accounting for the cognitive mechanisms, hesitation, or rhythm of reflection that characterize human players.

In response to this limitation, several recent studies have attempted to bring artificial intelligence models closer to human behavior. The Maia project, developed by the University of Toronto, proposes neural networks trained to imitate the moves played by humans at different skill levels. In a more applied context, platforms such as chess.com have introduced bots inspired by famous players, designed to reproduce their playing styles.

Despite these advances, an essential dimension of human chess remains largely absent from current approaches: thinking time. Existing models play their moves instantly, breaking the natural rhythm of a chess game and limiting immersion for human players. Yet the time spent thinking is a central component of the decision-making process. It depends on the complexity of the position, the phase of the game, time pressure, and psychological factors that are difficult to model explicitly.

The objective of this project is to explore the possibility of empirically modeling the thinking time of a human player from real game data. More precisely, we aim to predict the time required to play a given move as a function of the game context. The study focuses on games played by Magnus Carlsen, World Chess Champion, whose publicly available data are abundant and well documented. The analysis is deliberately restricted to blitz games, in which players typically have three to five minutes for the entire game, with a variable increment. This format imposes strong temporal constraints and makes time management strategies particularly salient.

In the short term, this work aims to demonstrate that human thinking time can be predicted in a non-trivial way from variables that are accessible in real time. In the longer term, such an approach could be integrated into existing systems, such as human-imitative chess bots, to enhance their realism and credibility in both scientific and applied settings.

Methodology

Data

The data used in this study consist of games played by Magnus Carlsen, publicly available in PGN (Portable Game Notation) format on the chess.com platform. PGN is a standard format that stores the complete record of a chess game, including moves, clock information, player metadata, and annotations.

The PGN files were processed using the python-chess library, which enables reliable parsing of games, precise identification of moves played by each player, and extraction of structural information about board positions. From these files, a dataset was constructed in the form of a dataframe in which each row corresponds to a single move played by Magnus Carlsen.

For each move, several categories of variables were extracted. These include temporal variables such as remaining time on the clock, increment associated with the time control, and time spent on the previous move; positional variables such as the number of legal moves and the phase of the game; game-dynamic variables such as captures and checks; and metadata related to the opponent and the time control. The target variable, denoted TimeSpent, corresponds to the actual time spent by Magnus Carlsen to play a given move. A detailed description of all variables is provided in the appendix.

Models

Several families of models were evaluated to assess their ability to predict thinking time. First, simple linear models were used, including linear regression, Ridge regression, and Lasso regression. These models serve as baseline references and provide insight into the intrinsic linearity of the problem.

Second, a Random Forest regressor was trained to capture potentially complex, non-linear relationships between explanatory variables and the target variable. Finally, a multilayer perceptron neural network was tested to explore the performance of more flexible parametric models.

For the non-linear models, a hyperparameter search was conducted to optimize performance. Models were evaluated using multiple metrics, with a particular focus on the coefficient of determination R^2 , which measures the proportion of variance in the target variable explained by the model, as well as error-based metrics such as mean squared error and root mean squared error.

Special attention was paid to variable selection. Some variables were deliberately excluded to ensure compatibility with real-time use cases, where computational constraints are critical. A more detailed discussion of these choices is provided in the appendix.

Results et discussion

The results obtained for the different models are summarized below.

Type of model	R ²	MSE	RMSE
Linear regression	0.084	35.920	5.993
Random Forest	0.501	19.56	4.42
Réseau de neurones	0.110	34.884	5.906

Clear differences emerge between the model families. Linear models exhibit very limited performance, with an R² close to 0.08. These results indicate that the relationship between explanatory variables and thinking time cannot be adequately captured by simple linear combinations.

Non-linear models achieve substantially better performance. The Random Forest model reaches an R² of 0.50, with an average error of approximately 4.4 seconds. This suggests that nearly half of the variance in human thinking time can be explained by observable features of the position and game context, which is a meaningful result given the inherently noisy and partially subjective nature of human decision-making.

The Random Forest emerges as the most stable and effective model in this study. Although performance could be further improved, these results confirm the feasibility of the approach and demonstrate that human thinking time is not purely random, but depends on measurable contextual factors.

Several avenues for future work can be identified. Increasing the volume of available data would likely reduce estimation variance and improve generalization. Incorporating additional features related to positional structure or strategic importance of moves could further enhance predictive performance. Data quality also represents an important limitation, as thinking times are rounded to the nearest second, introducing non-negligible noise into the target variable.

Beyond the specific case of Magnus Carlsen, building models tailored to individual players should be viewed not as an end in itself, but as a means to address the broader challenge of modeling human thinking time in chess. Ultimately, the goal would be to develop more general models capable of estimating thinking time as a function of player rating, playing style, and game format. One possible approach would involve clustering

players based on behavioral patterns extracted from online platforms, followed by training specialized models for different skill levels and styles. Such segmentation could improve predictive performance while limiting variance issues. This line of research could naturally extend existing projects such as Maia by adding a temporal dimension that is currently absent.

Data Availability

All data used in this study are publicly available.

The raw game data consist of 250 PGN files corresponding to blitz games played by Magnus Carlsen on chess.com. In addition, the processed datasets used for training and evaluation are provided as CSV files.

Both the raw PGN files and the processed datasets are archived on Zenodo and can be accessed via the following repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/18230736>

The GitHub repository associated with this project contains the full source code and experimental pipeline but does not include large data files or trained models, which are instead referenced through Zenodo to ensure long-term accessibility and reproducibility.

Bibliography

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2. McIlroy-Young, R., Wang, R., Sen, S., Kleinberg, J., Anderson, A. (2021). *Learning Personalized Models of Human Behaviour in Chess*
3. De Sa, C. (2012). *Classifying Chess Positions*
4. Vallance, L. (2018). *Exploring the Python Chess Module*

Appendix

PGN Data Format

PGN is a widely used standard in chess for storing moves, clock information, and game metadata. Its structured nature, combined with libraries such as python-chess, enables systematic extraction of features relevant for machine learning.

Variable Selection

Some initially considered variables, particularly those relying on chess engine evaluations, proved computationally expensive. In a real-time context, such costs are incompatible with a smooth user experience. In addition, some opponent-related variables are poorly distributed, as Magnus Carlsen primarily faces very high-level opponents. Including these variables could hinder model generalization. For these reasons, a careful variable selection was performed to test lighter and more application-oriented models.